

A Comprehensive Study for Assessing the Demand and Supply Dynamics of Parkinson's Disease Medication in Roorkee, Uttarakhand

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Publication history: Received on 10th April; Revised on 12th May; Accepted on 16th May 2024

Article DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11521486

Abstract: Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta region of the midbrain. This depletion of dopamine, a neurotransmitter crucial for regulating movement, leads to the characteristic motor symptoms of PD, including tremors, rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability. In India, the prevalence of PD is increasing, necessitating greater attention to the availability and distribution of appropriate medication. This comprehensive study aims to assess the demand and supply dynamics of PD medication in Roorkee, Uttarakhand. After recording the sales per week of various drugs, brands, dosage forms, and strengths available in Roorkee, it was determined that SINEMET (Carbidopa + Levodopa) is widely accessible in the region, with STALEVO, MIRAPEX (Pramipexole), and ARTANE (Trihexyphenidyl) being the other prominent brands available in local medical stores. These medications are primarily in tablet form. Sales data from different stores indicated that SINEMET (Carbidopa + Levodopa 25/250 mg) is the most popular drug in the Roorkee area for treating PD. In terms of drug type analysis, levodopa-based decarboxylase inhibitors, particularly the combination of Levodopa and Carbidopa, currently hold a dominant position in the PD drug market in the region.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, SINEMET, Levodopa, Carbidopa, Pramipexole, Trihexyphenidyl.

1. Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a chronic and progressive neurodegenerative disorder that primarily affects the motor system. It is characterized by the selective degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta, a region of the midbrain responsible for producing dopamine, a neurotransmitter essential for coordinating movement [1]. The loss of dopamine-producing neurons leads to a deficiency of dopamine in the striatum, a region of the brain involved in motor control, resulting in the characteristic motor symptoms of PD, such as tremors, rigidity, bradykinesia (slowness of movement), and postural instability [2]. The increasing prevalence of PD is a global concern, and it is estimated that more than 10 million people worldwide are affected by this condition [3]. The exact causes of PD are not fully understood, but it is believed to be a multifactorial disorder involving genetic and environmental factors, as well as aging [4-6]. While PD is primarily considered a movement disorder, it can also involve non-motor symptoms, such as cognitive impairment, depression, sleep disturbances, and autonomic dysfunction [7]. The treatment of PD aims to alleviate the motor symptoms and improve the overall quality of life for patients. The primary pharmacological approach involves the administration of dopamine precursors, such as levodopa, in combination with other medications that enhance the bioavailability and efficacy of levodopa [8]. Levodopa, in combination with carbidopa (a peripheral decarboxylase inhibitor), remains the gold standard treatment for PD [9]. However, as the disease progresses, the effectiveness of levodopa can diminish, and patients may experience motor complications, such as dyskinesias (involuntary movements) and fluctuations in response to the medication [10].

The global market for PD treatments is expected to grow significantly in the coming years, driven by the increasing prevalence of the disease, the aging population, and the development of new therapeutic approaches [2]. In India, the rise in demand for combination therapies, prolonged-action drugs, gene therapy, and government funding initiatives contribute to the market expansion for PD treatments [3]. This study aims to assess the demand and supply dynamics of PD medication in Roorkee, Uttarakhand, by analyzing the availability of various brands, dosages, and strengths of anti-Parkinson drugs in local medical stores, as well as the rate of sales. Understanding the demand and supply dynamics is crucial for ensuring that patients have access to the

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medications they need, thereby improving their quality of life and managing the symptoms of the disease more effectively. Additionally, this research can identify potential gaps in the market, helping policymakers and healthcare providers make informed decisions to enhance healthcare access and delivery for individuals living with PD in Roorkee. This review discusses various aspects of drug delivery systems, including targeted drug delivery strategies that exploit biological markers for site-specific action, controlled release mechanisms that sustain drug levels over extended periods, and nanotechnology applications that enable novel delivery platforms with enhanced efficacy and safety profiles.

2. Methodology

2.1. Preparation of Questionnaire

A questionnaire was prepared to conduct the survey of different medical shops for drugs used in the treatment of PD. The questionnaire included the following questions:

- How many drugs are available in your store for the treatment of Parkinson's disease?
- How many different brands of anti-Parkinson drugs are available in your medical store?
- What are the different anti-Parkinson dosage forms available in your medical store?
- What are the different strengths of anti-Parkinson drugs available in your medical store?
- What are the sales of different anti-Parkinson medicines per week?
- What are the sales of different brands of anti-Parkinson drugs per week?
- What are the sales of different anti-Parkinson dosage forms per week?
- What are the sales of different strengths of anti-Parkinson drugs per week?

2.2. Identification and Survey of Medical Stores

Table 1. List of the surveyed medical stores

S No.	Name of Medical Store	Address
1	Anuj Medical Store	Ram Nagar ,Roorkee
2	Vimal Medical store	Civil line , Roorkee
3	Focus Medical store	Malviya chowk ,Roorkee
4	Ayush Medical store	Malviya chowk ,Roorkee
5	Ganpati medical Store	Malviya chowk ,Roorkee
6	Apna medical store	Ganeshpur ,Roorkee
7	Kirti Medical Store	Azad Nagar,Roorkee
8	Altmas Medical Store	Railway Road ,Roorkee
9	Anand Medical store	Azad Nagar, Roorkee
10	Rawat Medical store	Bochhari, Roorkee
11	Super medicose	Rampur Chungi,Roorkee
12	Neelam Medical store	Malviya chowk ,Roorkee
13	Kamal Medical store	Civil line , Roorkee
14	Apollo Medical store	Civil line , Roorkee
15	Ahuja Medical store	Ram Nagar ,Roorkee
16	Mediwise Pharmacy	Aavas vikas Ramnagar,Roorkee
17	Aryan Medical store	Ram Nagar,Roorkee
18	National Medical store	Malviya chowk, Roorkee
19	Om Medical store	RamNagar,Roorkee
20	Pooja Medical store	Ram Nagar,Roorkee
21	Relan Medical store	Ram Nagar,Roorkee

Approximately 20 medical stores in the Roorkee region were identified for conducting the survey. After identification, the survey was conducted according to the above-mentioned questions at the selected medical stores in the Roorkee region. Table 1 provides a list of the surveyed medical stores and their addresses

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

The survey includes information on the availability and demand of various brands, dosages, and strengths of anti-Parkinson drugs in medical stores across different areas of Roorkee. Table 2 presents the compiled data, including the name of the medical store, brand name, composition and strength, dosage form, and sales per week of anti-Parkinson drugs. Additionally, the following figures illustrate the comparison data and plots of the sale of strips per week of anti-Parkinson drugs available at different medical stores in Roorkee.

Table 2. Name of Medical Store, Brands, Composition & strength, Dosage Forms, Sale strip per week of Anti-Parkinson drug

S.No.	Name of Medical Stores	Brand Name	Composition & Strength	Dosage Form	Sales Per Week
1	Anuj Medical store,Ram Nagar, Roorkee	SINEMET	Carbidopa+Levodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	15 strip
		AZILECT	Rasagiline1 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		MIRAPEX	Pramipexole0.25 mg	Tablets	16 strip
2	Vimal Medical Store, Civil line , Roorkee	REQUIP OR REQUIP XL	Ropinirol0.25 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		AMANTADIN	Amantadin100 mg	Tablets	18 strip
		COMTAN	Antacapone	Capsule	15 strip
		SINEMENT	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	18 strip
3	Focus Medical store,Malviya Chowk,Roorkee	MIRAPEXOR	Pramipexole0.25 mg	Tablets	20 strip
		MIRAPEXER			
		COGENTIN	Benzotropine2 mg	Tablets	14 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine75 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
4	Ayush Medical store,Malviya Chowk, Roorkee	ELDEPRYL	Selegiline5 mg	Tablets	20 strip
		AKILETON	Biperiden10 mg	Tablets	18 strip
		STALEVO	Entacapone 100 mg	Capsule	15 strip
		MIRAPEX	Pramipexole0.25 mg	Tablets	17strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	15 strip
5	Ganpati Medical stores,Malviya Chowk,Roorkee	ARTAN	Trihexyphenidyl 250 mg	Tablets	20strip
		COGENTIN	Benzotropine2 mg	Tablets	16 strip

		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	17 strip
		EXELON	Rivastigmine 3mg	Tablets	16 strip
6	Apna Medical stores,Ganeshpur,Roorkee	APOKYN	Apomorphine10 mg	Tablets	22 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine75 mg	Tablets	20 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	15 strip
		PARCOPA	Carbidopa 0.1 mg	Tablets	18 strip
7	Kirti Medicose Azad Nagar , Roorkee	SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa 25/250 mg	Tablets	20 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine75 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		MIRAPEX	Pramipexole0.25 mg	Tablets	18 strip
		AKILETON	Biperiden 10 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		COGENTIN	Benzotropine2 mg	Tablets	16 strip
8	Altmas Medical Store,Railway station road, Roorkee	ARTAN	Trihexyphenidyl 250 mg	Tablets	14 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa 25/250 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		COGENTIN	Benzotropine 2 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		EXELON	Rivastigmine 3 mg	Tablets	12 strip
9	Aanand Medical store, Azad Nagar Roorkee	APOKYN	Apomorphine 10 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine75 mg	Tablets	8 strip
		STALEVO	Entacapone 100 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa 25/250 mg	Tablets	16 strip
10	Rawat Medical store,Roorkee	ELDEPRYL	Selegiline5 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		STALEVO	Entacapone 100 mg	Tablets	14 strip
		MIRAPEX	Pramipexole 0.25 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa 25/250 mg	Tablets	17 strip
11	Super medicose,Rampur chungi , Roorkee	APOKYN	Apomorphine 10 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine 75 mg	Tablets	14 strip
		STALEVO	Entacapone 100 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Levodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
12	Neelam Medical Store, Civil line , Roorkee	MIRAPEX	Pramipexole 0.25 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		STALEVO	Entacapone 100 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		ELDEPRYL	Selegiline 5 mg	Tablets	8 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Levodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
13	Kamal Medical Store, Civil line , Roorkee	MIRAPEX	Pramipexole 0.25 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		AZILECT	Rasagiline 1 mg	Tablets	16 strip

		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Levodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
14	Apollo Pharmacy, Roorkee	REQUIP OR REQUIP XL	Ropinirol 0.25 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		AMANTADIN	Amantadin 100 mg	Tablets	10 strip
		COMTAN	Antacapone 200 mg	Tablets	12 strip
15	Ahuja Medical store, Ramanagar, Roorkee	ARTAN	Trihexyphenidyl 250 mg	Tablets	14 strip
		COGENTIN	Benztropine 2 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
16	Mediwise Pharmacy,Aavas vikas Ramnagar, Roorkee	APOKYN	Apomorphine 10 mg	Tablets	20 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine 75 mg	Tablets	10 strip
		PARCOPA	Carbidopa 0.1 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		SINEMET	Carbidopa+Levodopa 25/250 mg	Tablets	14 strip
17	Aaryan Medical store, Ram nagar , Roorkee	SINEMET	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		NEUTRON	Rotigotine 75 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		MIRAPEX	Pramipexole 0.25 mg	Tablets	10 strip
		AKILETON	Biperiden 10 mg	Tablets	16 strip
18	National Medical store,Malviya chowk , Roorkee	ARTAN	Trihexyphenidyl 250 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		COGENTIN	Benztropine 2 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		EXELON	Rivastigmine 3mg	Tablets	14 strip
19	Pooja Medical store,Ram nagar,	REQUIP OR	Ropinirol 0.25 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		REQUIP XL			
		AMANTADIN	Amantadin 100 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		COMTAN	Antacapone 200 mg	Tablets	10 strip
		SINEMENT	Carbidopa+Livodopa25/250 mg	Tablets	12 strip
20	Relan Medical store, Rampur chungi, Roorkee	REQUIP OR	Ropinirol 0.25 mg	Tablets	16 strip
		REQUIP XL			
		AMANTADIN	Amantadin100 mg	Tablets	14 strip

		COMTAN	Antacapone 200 mg	Tablets	16 strip
21	Satish Medical store,Ram nagar , Roorkee	MIRAPEX	Pramipexole 0.25 mg	Tablets	20 strip
		STALEVO	Entacapone 100 mg	Tablets	12 strip
		ELDEPRYL	Selegiline 5 mg	Tablets	16 strip

3.2. Discussion

The study revealed several key insights into the demand and supply dynamics of PD medication in the Roorkee region of Uttarakhand. Notably, SINEMET (Carbidopa + Levodopa), a combination drug that serves as the gold standard treatment for PD [11], was widely available and had the highest sales across multiple medical stores in the region. This finding aligns with the established efficacy and widespread use of levodopa-based therapies in the management of PD symptoms [12-14].

Other prominent brands available in the local medical stores included STALEVO (Entacapone), MIRAPEX (Pramipexole), and ARTANE (Trihexyphenidyl). These medications represent different classes of PD drugs, such as dopamine agonists (Pramipexole) and anticholinergics (Trihexyphenidyl), which are often used as adjunct therapies or alternatives to levodopa, depending on the stage and specific symptoms of the disease [15-17]. The dominance of SINEMET (Carbidopa + Levodopa) in the Roorkee market aligns with the global trend, where levodopa-based decarboxylase inhibitors remain the cornerstone of PD treatment [18]. The combination of levodopa and carbidopa helps to improve the bioavailability and efficacy of levodopa by preventing its premature metabolism in the periphery [19, 20]. This approach allows for lower doses of levodopa to be administered, thereby reducing the risk of adverse effects while maintaining therapeutic efficacy.

The availability of other PD medications, such as dopamine agonists (e.g., Pramipexole) and anticholinergics (e.g., Trihexyphenidyl), in the Roorkee medical stores highlights the need for a comprehensive treatment approach in managing PD. These adjunct therapies can be beneficial in addressing specific symptoms or complications associated with the disease, such as motor fluctuations, dyskinesias, or non-motor symptoms like tremors or cognitive impairment [21, 22]. It is noteworthy that the survey data revealed a predominance of tablet formulations for PD medications in the Roorkee region. Tablets are a convenient and widely accepted dosage form, contributing to better patient adherence and ease of administration [15]. However, as PD progresses and patients experience difficulties in swallowing, alternative dosage forms, such as transdermal patches or subcutaneous injections, may become necessary to ensure optimal drug delivery and symptom management [16].

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the current landscape of PD medication availability and demand in the Roorkee region. However, it is crucial to consider the limitations of the study, such as the relatively small sample size of medical stores surveyed and the potential for variations in prescription patterns and patient preferences across different geographic locations. Future research could investigate the factors influencing the prescription patterns of PD medications in the region, including physician preferences, patient demographics, and disease severity. Additionally, studying the barriers to access and affordability of PD treatments could inform strategies to improve medication availability and adherence, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes.

4. Conclusion

This comprehensive study has shed light on the demand and supply dynamics of Parkinson's disease medication in the Roorkee region of Uttarakhand. The findings highlight the widespread availability and high demand for SINEMET (Carbidopa + Levodopa), the gold standard treatment for PD, as well as the presence of other adjunct therapies such as dopamine agonists and anticholinergics in the local medical stores. The dominance of levodopa-based decarboxylase inhibitors in the Roorkee market aligns with global trends in PD treatment, reflecting their proven efficacy and widespread acceptance. However, the availability of alternative therapies underscores the need for a personalized and comprehensive approach to managing PD symptoms and complications.

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